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AIR POLLUTION IN INDIA

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Abstract

Air pollution is an increasingly important environmental issue in urban areas. The rapid growth of motor vehicles along with the industrial development contributes to a definite air pollution pattern with clear trends of deteriorated air quality. Air pollution is basically the presence of foreign substances in the Air. "Air pollution is the excessive concentration of foreign matter in the air which adversely affects the well-being of the individual or causes damage to the property (*American, Medical Association*). Air pollution is not a recent phenomenon: King Edward I of England tried to clear the smoky sky over London in 1272 by banning the use of coal. The British Parliament ordered the torturing and hanging of man who sold and burned the outward coal. Under Richard II (1377-1399) and later under Henry V (1413~1422), England took steps to regulate and restrict the use of coal. Such natural processes as forest fires, decaying vegetation, dust storms and volcanic eruptions have always contaminated the air. Although the total global production of many gases and particulate matter recognized as pollutants is much greater from natural resources than from man-made sources, but global distribution and dispersion of those natural pollutants result in low average concentrations. By precipitation, oxidation and absorption into the ocean and the soil, atmosphere can clean itself of all known pollutants if given sufficient time. On the other hand, man generated pollutants are continuously emitted and concentrated in small geographic region; hence air pollution problem is generally anthropogenic phenomena. Presently the rate of pollutants discharged into the atmosphere in highly populated regions exceeds the natural cleaning rate of atmosphere. In the present research focused on the status of Air Pollution in India.

Keywords: Suspended Particles, Sulphur dioxide, Nitrogen oxides, Carbon monoxide. ozone and hydrocarbon pollutants

Status of Air Pollution in India

In most of the 23 Indian cities with million-plus population, air pollution level exceed the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended health standards. Further in almost every city, the levels are getting worse because of the growing vehicles, high energy consumption, uncontrolled industrialization and burning of waste.

Six out of India's 10 largest cities-Mumbai, Calcutta, Delhi, Ahmadabad, Kanpur and Nagpur face severe air pollution problems, The annual average levels of Total Suspended Particles (TSP) at least three times more than WHO standard. It has been associated with both premature death" from respiratory illness and cardiovascular diseases and increased morbidity (high incidence of chronic obstructive lung diseases,

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especially bronchitis and of upper and lower respiratory tract infections).

However, concentration of Sulphur dioxide and Nitrogen oxides are generally low compared to' ambient standard. Carbon monoxide .ozone and hydrocarbon pollutants that can have serious health impacts are not routinely monitored in India. CO reading at traffic intersections often has been found to be excess.

Table 1.1 will provide an idea of S02 and NO x in most of the Indian cities.

CLASSIFICATION OF POLLUTANTS

All air pollutants may be classified according to origin, chemical composition and state of matter. For clarity, this classification will be used to structure the discussion of air pollution parameters .

Origin

According to their origin, pollutants are considered as either primary or secondary contaminants. Primary pollutants like Sulphur Oxides (SO), Nitrogen Oxides (NO), and Hydrocarbons (HC) are emitted directly to the atmosphere and these are found in the form in which they were emitted. Secondary pollutants, such as, Ozone (O) and Perroxyacetyl Nitrate (PAN) are formed in the atmosphere by photochemical reaction.

Table 1.1 Annual average S02 and NO, concentration 'in the-ambient air in residential & industrial areas of cities with more than one million human population

City	Residential Area				Industrial Area			
	1995		2000		1995		2000	
	SO ₂	NO	SO ₂	NO	SO ₂	NO	SO ₂	NO
Agra	-	-	8.2	7.5	-	-	-	-
Ahmedabad	38.3	18.0	8.2	25.3	22.4	16.9	9.0	35.2
Bangalore	-	31.0	24.2	47.0	-	-	18.9-	32.4
Bhopal	11.5	18.2	19.7	20.2	13.1	21.3	22.0	26.0
Chennai	7.8	14.5	7.2	14.8	30.9	19.4	16:0	14.3
Delhi	16.2	33.0	16.0	29.4	20.4	34.6	17.4	33.7
Faridabad	37.0	13.3	36.5	11.1	39.1	14.7	37.3	11.5
Haora	84.0	2.12.2	13.4	50.2	39.8	180.6	12.4	51.4
Hyderabad	15.3	28.3	13.7	21.0	19.0	47.2	12.0	29.2
Indore	5.3	9.5	22.9.	16.6	7.3	11.7-	28.5	22.0
Jaipur	8.56	25.7	18.1	41.3	14.7	35.1	23.2	47.7
Kalyan-Dombivili- Ambamath	29.3	32.8	38.3	58.1	32.6	39.4	37.6	65.4
Kanpur	13.9	15.6	18.7	20.0	14.3	16.6	17.8	28.4
Kolkata	29.9	27.3	13.5	30.0	47.4	35.2	25.3	44.2
Lucknow	29.5	28.7	27.4*	29.0	30.4	29.1	-	-
Ludhiana	-	-	11.7	30.8	-	-	11.6	30.2
Mumbai	25.9	34.3	10.5	29.0-	41.8	36.1	15.4	25.0
Nagpur	8.6	15.4	6.9	24.4	7.9	11.8	8.0	17.7
Nashik	-	31.0	33.8	23.2	-	-	28.8	17.3
Patna	26.2	29.0	14.0	17.0	-	-	-	-
Puile	7.8	8.5	43.3	63.1	37.3	38.4	43.6	57.6
Surat	84.5	30.8	-	-	88.6	29.8	-	-
Vadodara	66.2	18.5	-	-	76.6	20.4	-	-
Varanasi	23.6	19.6	18.9	17.5	-	-	-	-

Source: National Air Quality Status Report - 2000: Central Pollution Control Board.

Chemical Composition

Pollutants whether primary or secondary, may be further classified according to chemical composition as either organic or inorganic. Organic compounds contain carbon and hydrocarbon and may also contain elements, such as, Oxygen, Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Sulphur, Hydrocarbons or organic compounds containing only carbon and hydrogen. Inorganic compounds found in contaminated _ atmosphere that include carbon monoxide (CO), Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Carbonates, Sulphur Oxides, Nitrogen Oxides, Ozone, Hydrogen Fluoride and Hydrogen Chloride.

State of Matter

Pollutants can also be further classified as particulate or gaseous. The following table shows the classification of pollutants

Table 1.2 Classification of Pollutants

Major Pollutants	Sub- Pollutants	Typical Members of Sub-Classes
Particulates	Solid	Dust, smoke, fumes, fly ash, mist, spray etc.
Gases	Hydrocarbons	Hexane, benzene, ethylene, methane, butadiene etc.
Organic	Aldehydes and ketones, Other organics	Formaldehyde, acetone Chlorinated hydrocarbons, Alcohols
Inorganic	Oxides of Carbon Oxides of Sulphur Oxides of Nitrogen Other inorganic	Carbon monoxide, Carbon dioxide Sulphur dioxide, Sulphur trioxide Nitrogen dioxide, Nitric oxide Hydrogen sulfide, Hydrogen fluoride, ammoma

Particulates

Air quality parameters fall into two broad categories, particulate matter which may be liquid or solid, and gases matter. Particulates are any dispersed matter, solid or liquid, in which the individual aggregates are larger than a single small molecule (about 0.002 μ m) but smaller than about 500 μ m. Particulates may be classified and discussed according to their physical, chemical, or biological characteristics. Physical characteristics include size, mode of formation, settling properties and optical qualities. Chemical characteristics include organic or inorganic composition and biological characteristics related to their classification as bacteria, viruses, spores etc.

Oxides of Sulphur

The oxides of Sulphur (SO_x) are probably the most widespread and the most intensively studied of all anthropogenic air pollutants. They include six different gaseous compounds namely Sulphur monoxide (SO), Sulphur dioxide (SO₂), Sulphur trioxide (SO₃), Sulphur tetraoxide (SO₄), Sulphur sesquioxide (S₂O₃) and Sulphure heptoxide (S₂O₇). Sulphur dioxide and Sulphur trioxide are two oxides of Sulphur of most important in the study of air pollution. Sulphur dioxide is colourless, nonflammable, and non-explosive gas with a suffocating odour. It has taste threshold of 784 g/m³ (0.3 ppm) and an odour threshold of 1306 g/m³ (0.5 ppm).

It is estimated that SO₂ remains airborne for average of 2 to 4 days. During this duration it may be

. transported as far as 1000 km. Thus, the problem of SO₂ pollution is not local but regional one and sometimes international.

Oxides of Nitrogen

Oxides of Nitrogen are the second most abundant atmospheric contaminants in many cities ranking next to Sulphur dioxide. Generally highest contributor of the nitrogen oxides is industries which are producing it or using it in manufacturing processes. The next highest contributor is transport sector, and then comes large power plants. Oxides of Nitrogen (NO_x) includes six gases compounds namely Nitric Oxide (NO), Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) Nitrogen oxide (N₂O), Nitrogen sesquioxide (N₂O₃), Nitrogen tetroxide (N₂O₄) and Nitrogen pentoxide (N₂O₅) Nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) are the two oxides of nitrogen of primary concern in air pollution.

At high temperatures, nitrogen and oxygen in the air react to form nitric oxide. NO is further oxidized in the atmosphere to nitrogen dioxide. NO dissolves in water to give HNO₃. Atmospheric HNO₃ is also formed by reaction of water vapour with N₂O₅ produced by the oxidation of NO₂ by ozone. Out of all the oxides of nitrogen, nitrous oxide, (N₂O) is the most stable in troposphere (estimated lifetime 4000 days at 10 km); however, it may be photo dissociated at higher levels (estimated lifetime 20 days at 40 km). The average residence time of NO₂ in the atmosphere is also about 2 months because it is readily washed down as nitrate by rain. Nitric oxide is also synthesized in the atmosphere during thunderstorms.

Ozone (Photochemical Oxidants)

High emission of hydrocarbons and NO_x during bright sunshine causes chemical reactions in the atmosphere producing photochemical oxidants. The photochemical processes are complex, it takes place over several hours and result in the formation of ozone (O₃) Nitrogen dioxide (NO), peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN), a variety of the gaseous compounds that are poorly defined, and very fine particulate matter. Ozone is the strongest of the photo chemically formed oxidants that are stable enough to be identified and measured.

Ozone exists in great abundance under natural conditions In the stratosphere (upper atmosphere). Photochemical air pollution occurs predominantly in highly motorized areas and where inversion conditions prevail. Photochemical smog is formed due to oxidation of hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides. It has been found that at the time of photochemical smog formation, there is considerable increase in amount of Ozone and oxidant materials at troposphere (lower atmosphere)

In troposphere, ozone is not found in appreciable amounts at night, but only during the day it begins to form. These facts clearly indicate that photochemical formation of ozone or oxidant from . impurities takes place due to the action of sunlight.

The most important ozone reaction in the troposphere that involves NO₂ is described below.

Thus, any activity that increases atmospheric nitrogen dioxide concentration would generate more ozone. This is particularly so in a polluted atmosphere containing nitrogen oxides. The residence time of ozone in the troposphere is one to two months.

Oxides of Carbon

Carbon dioxide and Carbon Monoxide are the principal air pollutants. Main anthropogenic source of these pollutants are fossil fuels. Forest fire and volcanoes are natural sources of these pollutants. During complete combustion of fossil fuels, carbon atoms in the fuel combine with oxygen molecules to form CO₂, High level of CO₂ in air may cause difficulty in breathing and respiration.

The process of combustion is rarely complete, the incomplete combustion may occur when the oxygen supply is insufficient, combustion temperature is too low or when residence time in combustion chamber is too short. Carbon monoxide (CO) is product of incomplete combustion. It is completely invisible, it is colorless

odourless and tasteless gas.

Almost 70 per cent of Carbon monoxide emission comes from automobiles sector. It is also a principal component of "photochemical smog".

SOURCES OF AIR POLLUTION

Sources of Air Pollution can be broadly classified as:

- Natural Sources; and
- Anthropogenic (man-made) Sources.

Natural Sources

The natural sources of air pollution occur naturally. As man cannot control nature, therefore air pollution by natural sources cannot be controlled. A few natural sources are presented below:

i) Volcanic Eruptions

Eject pollutants like particulate matter, dust, fly ash along with various gases, such as, sulphur dioxide (SO₂)

ii) Process of Pollination

This process is carried out by plants with the help of wind. In this case the pollen grains are carried away by wind as pollutants.

iii) Desert Storms or Dust Storms

In the deserts or arid or semi-arid areas, the sand or dust particles are carried by wind as pollutants. This is due to absence of moisture in the soil.

iv) Forest Fires These fires are caused due to friction of trees or grass against each other or by lightning striking on them. the pollutants obtained from forest fires are Carbon monoxide (CO), Carbon dioxide (CO₂), particulates, Hydrocarbons (HC), Oxides of Nitrogen (NO), etc.

Anthropogenic Sources

Air Pollution caused by human activities are termed as anthropogenic pollution, it is further classified i as stationary sources, and mobile-sources.

i) Stationary Sources

Various stationary sources include industrial and commercial process, generation of heat or power (electricity), stationary engines, home heating, cooking, refuse burning, incineration, and use of solvents/aerosols.

ii) Mobile Sources are:

Line Source: highway vehicles, trains, and channel vessels.

Area Source: railway yards, port vessels. junctions, and aerodrome.

EFFECTS OF AIR POLLUTION

The major air pollutants may cause direct and indirect effect on humans and environment.

- Health Effects: Irritation of respiratory, eye or other systems; acute toxic systematic effects; mutagenic or carcinogenic actions; and adverse effects on defense mechanisms against infections.
- Ecological Effects: material soiling, corrosion, loss of agricultural productivity, acidification of soil and water, forest die-back, greenhouse effects; smog formation etc.

Certain of these effects may be immediately apparent and relatively easy to trace its source. For example the odour of the diesel smoke and other effects may occur in the short terms but the ' precise contribution of vehicle emissions to these is not 'always clear. Certain effects may take long , period to become apparent and drawing a casual-link to the source of emissions become more difficult and complicated as is the case with many carcinogens; Some of these pollutants have also been implicated in more complex environmental problems, such as, photochemical smog, acid precipitation and Green house effects.

Until recently, attention to air pollution problems has been focused on the effects of individual pollutants. However, growing evidence is emerging that the problem may be much greater with the combination of the

individual pollutants. For example, a careful review of the 'dying German forests indicates that it may be due to synergistic effects of both acid rain and photochemical reaction products, as well as direct effects of SO₂ and NO₂. Other studies have found that adverse health effects from SO₂ and NO₂ in combination is much more serious than from these pollutants individually. It has been noted, "... high level of SO₂ and co-existing particulate pollutants have been associated with increase in respiratory mortality rates". Therefore, considering the effects of these, pollutants separately may lead to erroneous conclusions regarding the relative and absolute need for cost effectiveness of control measures.

"Health' Effects

Carbon onoxide

The toxic properties of this gas are due to its ability to react with the haemoglobin in the blood to produce carboxy-haemoglobin (COHb). Carbon monoxide has greater affinity for haemoglobin than oxygen and it is preferentially absorbed even when the concentration of carbon monoxide is very low. The degree of absorption depends upon the concentration of carbon monoxide in the air, mat is, the period of exposure and the activity of the individual. The toxic effects of carbon monoxide ,as measured by the percentage of carboxy-haemoglobin in the blood are given below (Table 1.3).

After a person ceases to be exposed to non-lethal dose of carbon dioxide, the carboxy haemoglobin content of the blood gradually declines by (50% in 3 to 4 hours) as carbon monoxide is breathed out. Table 1.3 shows the signs and symptoms at various concentrations of Carboxy haemoglobin (CoHb) per cent.

Table 1.3: Effect of CO on Human Health

COHb%	Signs and Symptoms for an average person
Less than 1	No signs or symptoms.
1-2	Tiighness across the forehead, possible slight headache, dilation of the skin blood vessel. Headache and throbbing in the temples.
2-3	Severe headache, weakness, dizziness, dimness of vision, nausea, vomiting; and collapse. Syncope, .increased pulse rate, coma, intermittent convulsions and Cheyne-strokes respiration. Coma, intermittent copvulsions, depressed heart action and respiratory rate-
5-6	and possible death Weak pulse, slow respirations, respiratory-failure
6	and death within a few hours. Death within a few minutes.

Source: Peavy , *Environmental Engineering,*

CO can affect driving ability (JJ1dalso impaired oxygen transport in the human body. It can have ,serious implications for Persons with pre- existing heart and lung problem. It is also very harmful for the fetus, carried by pregnant women.

Oxides of Nitrogen

The toxicity of NO₂ is very much higher than NO. Maximum allowable concentration for industrial exposures for NO & NO₂ is 25 ppm & 5 ppm respectively, Normal levels in city streets are under 1 per cent of these values; therefore little information is available on their effects on human health.

Studies have indicated that exposure NO₂ can be linked with increase susceptibility to respiratory infection, increased airway resistance in asthmatic persons and decreased. pulmonary function. Short-term exposures to NO₂ have-resulted in different types of respiratory problems in school children, such as, coughs and sore

throats at concentrations typically higher than normal air quality standards. The possibility of effects from continuous exposure to very low levels remains a worry.

Photochemical Oxidants

The O₃, NO₂ and PAN are highly active oxidizing chemicals and are responsible for most of the injury and damage produced by this type of air pollution. The fine particulate matter, which consists mainly of nitrates and sulphates, interferes considerably with visibility and is one of the major annoyance factors. Another is the eye irritation caused partly by PAN and partly by other chemicals in the poorly defined group, such as formaldehyde and acrolein is another important impact.

The indoor ozone is known to be highly toxic and there are enough evidence, according to the World Health Organization, for attributing many adverse effects solely to ozone. Studies have shown that many people, suffer adverse effects from exposure to ozone at quite low levels including eye irritation, coughs, chest discomfort, headaches, respiratory illness, increased asthma attacks, and reduced pulmonary function. The indoor ozone is more significant in closed areas, such as, buildings sealed for air conditioning.

Lead

Lead enters the body either through mouth, or breathed in through the nose. Ingested lead is less absorbed than inhaled. The rate of absorption also depends on its chemical composition, the volatile organic lead compounds added to petrol being more readily absorbed than the inorganic particulate products of combustion. Poisoning by lead at high concentration has been recognized for a very long time. The most common form of lead poisoning is the disturbance of the gastrointestinal system known as lead colic, excessive tiredness, continued headaches, loss of appetite, nausea, and muscular pains. .

Toxicological studies have demonstrated that three systems in the body, most sensitive to lead are the blood forming system, the nervous system and the renal system. Reproductive endocrine, cardiovascular and gastrointestinal function may also be affected by lead. In children it can inhibit enzymatic system.

Hydrocarbon

There is no doubt that they have a carcinogenic effect, and that they commonly occur in smoke from the incomplete combustion of hydrocarbon fuels of all kinds.

The studies have shown that, particular organic compound, such as, aldehydes, polycyclic aromatic compound, and benzene have adverse effects on human health. But however molecular hydrocarbon is relatively nontoxic, although they may cause, unpleasant effects including eye irritation, coughing, sneezing and symptom akin to drunkenness. Benzene is well known human carcinogen causing leukemia

Oxide of Sulphur

Sulphur dioxide tends to irritate the mucous membrane of respiratory track and foster the development of chronic respiratory disease, particularly' bronchitis. Exposure at SO₂ level of about 1ppm (2600 g/m³) leads to the constriction of air passages in respiratory tract, often SO₂ gets absorbed on the surface of very fine particles and is carried deep into the lungs. In dusty atmosphere, SO₂ is particularly harmful because particulates with Sulphur dioxide and Sulphuric acid molecule paralyze the hair like cilia, which line the respiratory tract. These particulates usually carry with them concentrated amount of SO₂ thus bringing this irritant into direct and prolonged contact with delicate lung tissues.

Particulate Matter

Particulate matter is emitted along with exhaust as well as flue gases. Fine particulate matter may be toxic in itself or may carry toxic (including carcinogenic) trace substances absorbed on its surface.

The size of particulate inhaled is very important for the success and failure of respiratory defense. , Approximately 40 per cent of particulate between 1 and 2 μm in size are retained in bronchi and alveoli as shown in figure 9.1. It has been found that particulate matter aggravate disease, such as, bronchitis, asthma and influenza. Diesel particulates are of major concern because of its carcinogenicity. The possibility of developing cancer may be 42 per cent greater in individual

exposed to 'diesel exhaust than others.

Figure 1.1: (a) Human Respiratory Tract (b) Bronchiole and Alveolar Structure

Ecological Effects

Road Side Pollutant

Vegetation close to a heavy traffic road, in vicinity of thermal power plants and cement industries, is subjected to high concentration of air born pollutants. According to a study done by Central Pollution Control Board, it is found that the plant bushes located near roadside have higher levels of lead.

Tomatoes are very sensitive and have been found to suffer at roadside concentration of NO_x and as result of particulate fall out, the vegetation becomes darkened and looks dusty. The road surface run off during rain contains high quantity of suspended solid lead, oil and bitumen. These have potential to affect severely the nearby water.

Ozone

Ozone is unique among gaseous pollutant; its high concentration at lower troposphere (near earth surface) is injurious to human health and ecosystem whereas low concentration at stratosphere is detrimental for our existence. The high concentration of ozone at lower troposphere damages plants species. There has been suggestion that ozone is a major factor contributing to the decline of forest health. It has many implications for human health and it may well affect crop production.

Acid Rain

The main precursors of acid rain or acid deposition in the form of snow are Sulphur dioxides (SO_2) and Nitrogen oxides (NO_x). The transport vehicle contribution is mostly in the form of NO_x . These chemicals react with rain water and other chemicals in the air to form sulfuric acid, nitric acid and other harmful pollutants like sulfates and nitrates. These acid pollutants spread upward into the atmosphere, and are carried by air currents to finally return to the ground in the form of acid rain, fog or snow. The corrosive nature of acid rain causes many forms of environmental damage especially to plant life.

Damage from acid rain is widespread all over the world. Coal burning and power plants contribute to about 70 per cent of sulphur dioxide in the atmosphere which in turn contributes to acid rain. Major effects of acid rain are:

- Acid rain erodes and washes away nutrients in the soil which are needed by plants. It can also dissolve naturally toxic substances like aluminum and mercury, freeing them to pollute water or poison plants
- It affects trees more directly by creating holes in the waxy coating of leaves, causing brown dead spots, which effects the plants photosynthesis. Spruce and fir forests at higher elevations seem to be most at risk.

Figure 1.2

Acid rain that falls or flows as ground water to reach rivers; lakes and wetlands, causes the water in them to become acidic. This affects plant and animal life in aquatic ecosystems.

- Acid rain and dry acid deposition damages buildings, automobiles, and other structures made of stone or metal. The acid corrodes the material causing extensive damage and ruins historic buildings. For instance the Parthenon in Greece and Taj Mahal in India have been affected by acid rain.

Green House Effect

Human activities during the past few centuries have polluted the atmosphere to the extent that it has begun to seriously affect the climate. The carbon dioxide in the atmosphere has increased by 31 per cent since preindustrial times, causing more heat to be trapped in the lower atmosphere.

There is evidence to show that carbon dioxide levels are increasing. Many countries have signed a convention to reduce greenhouse gases (GHGs) under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). However, the current international agreements are still not effective enough to prevent the significant changes in climate and a rise in sea level.

Fossil fuel consumption agricultural, deforestation and present land-use practices contribute to the CO₂ buildup. Continued CO₂ buildup will lead significant enough rise in earth surface temperature to melt the Arctic ice pack. If the warming trend can be confirmed and positively linked to CO₂ buildup, then global action, such as, reforestation may eventually have to be pursued to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere. In fact, this seems to be the case.

The amount of tropospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) is reported to be increasing at the rate of 1.8 J:1g1mp3er year, a process that may not be reversible. Furthermore, this increase has been accompanied by an equivalent decrease in atmospheric oxygen (O₂)' Currently, there is more than 700 billion tonnes of carbon in the form of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Each year this figure gets increased by 2.3 billion tonnes, i.e., a 3 per cent increase by every decade.

Fig. 1.3: Global Temperature Changes (1880-2000)

Greenhouse Effect

About 75 per cent of the solar energy reaching the earth is absorbed by earth's surface, which increases its temperature. The rest of the heat radiates back to the atmosphere. Some of the heat is trapped by greenhouse gases (GHGs), mostly carbon dioxide. As carbon dioxide is released by various human activities, it is rapidly increasing. This is causing global warming.

There is at present some uncertainty about the effect of global warming if it is allowed to continue. What harmful changes will occur if present trends continue is not a doubt but only doubt is about when and where they will occur and -their overall magnitude .

AIR QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Air unlike water, cannot be purified at central location and redistributed for use. Hence, extreme care must be taken for its protection. Air pollution can be controlled by following fundamental approaches:

Proper planning of industrial area like zoning;

- Proper stack design for wide dispersion of air pollutants;
- Prevention of air pollution by changing raw material, type of fuel, manufacturing process, etc.;
- Reduction in emission by using control equipments ,for example settling chamber, cyclones, electrostatic precipitator, scrubbers etc.; and
- Making adequate legislation and air quality standards.

Adopting zoning system at planning stage can effectively control air pollution. In this regard, zoning can be

done at macro (national level) as well as micro level (cities). The Center Pollution Control Board (CPCB) of Ministry of Environment and Forest of Government of India has developed a Zoning Atlas at national level for locating different types of industries. The atlas is prepared by considering many factors, such as, availability of natural resources, water, energy, and meteorological parameters like wind velocity, direction, mixing height, inversion layer etc.

If the height and top diameter of the stack are properly designed it can significantly help in reducing air pollution in the surrounding area. Stack height above the inversion layer disperses the contaminants in large volume of air. Dilution of pollutant in the air depends upon mixing height, wind direction and velocity, atmospheric temperature, and temperature of the flue gas emitted. The drawback of this approach is that it is short-term measure good for neighbouring area of pollution generation. However, "what goes up comes down"; Acid rain is notable example of air pollution problem that transcend local boundaries.

Energy substitution, such as, solar, hydraulic and geothermal energy will eliminate significantly the pollution caused by conventional fossil fuel combustion. Lead free (unleaded) petrol can eliminate lead emission from automobiles. Using low sulfur coal and oil would reduce SO₂ emissions. Coal washing before pulverization can reduce fly.ash emissions considerably. Change in manufacturing process can also reduce air pollution, for example use of electric furnace instead of open-hearth furnace in steel industry. Designing the storage tanks with floating roof covers in petroleum refineries can reduce loss of hydrocarbon vapours from storage tanks during filling. Use of exhaust hoods and ducts will not only reduce fugitive air pollution but also help in recovery of valuable solvents.

The most effective strategy for controlling air pollution is to prevent emission at source itself. Several types of air cleaning devices can collect or trap pollutants before they are emitted in the atmosphere. Pollution control equipment are generally classified as follows:

Until the mid 1990s air pollution was considered as state or local problem. However, today it is recognized as international problem of global scale. Air quality laws and guidelines are under constant review and are often modified. There are three basic types of guidelines, viz., threshold limit values, emission standard, and ambient air quality standards.

Threshold limit values (TLVs) focus on specific air contaminants that will recognize cause and health effects relationship. It serves primarily as occupational guidelines. TLVs are typically established on the basis of exposure for 8 hours/day, 5 days/week. Emission standards are focused on major air pollution generators of both stationary and mobile sources, such as, power plants, incinerators, oil refineries, stack emission from manufacturing plant, automobiles etc.

Ambient air quality standards set limit for outdoor atmospheric pollutants, their objective is to minimize the overall adverse effect of air pollutants on health, comfort and property. Exposure time is assumed to be 24 hours/day, 7 days/week. Ambient air quality standards are formed for particular regions. These regions are identified on the basis of meteorological and social factors.

Ambient Air Quality Standards

Air pollution is an increasingly important environment issue in urban areas. The rapid vehicular growth along with the industrial development contributes to a definite air pollution pattern with clear trends of deteriorated air quality in major cities. Rural air quality is affected by discharge of smoke from the use of crude fuels like wood, animal dung etc. in inefficient stoves. India's national ambient air quality standards are highlighted in the following table.

Table 1.4 National Ambient Air Quality Standards

Pollutants	Time weighted average	Concentration in ambient air		
		Industrial Areas	Residential, Rural & Other Areas	Sensitive Areas
Sulphur Dioxide	Annual Average	80 ug/m ³	60ug/m ³	15 ug/m ³
	24 Hours	120ug/m ³	80 ug/m ³	30.ug/m ³
Oxides of Nitrogen	Annual	80 ug/m ³	60ug/m ³	15 ug/m ³
	24 Hours	120ug/m ³	80 ug/m ³	30ug/m ³
Suspended Particulate Matter	Annual	360 ug/m ³	140ug/m ³	70u m ³
Respirable Particulate Matter (size less than 10mm)	24 Hours	500ug/m)	200ug/m ³	100ug/m ³ 50 ug/m ³
	Annual	120ug/m ³	60 ug/m ³	75 ug/m ³
Lead	24 Hours	150ug/m ³	100ug/m ³	0.50 ug/m ³
	Annual	1.0 ug/m ³	0.75 ug/m ³	0.75 ug/m ³
Carbon Monoxide	24 Hours	1.5 ug/m ³	1.00ug/m ³	2.0 ug/m ³
	Annual	5.0 ug/m ³	2.00 ug/m ³	2.0 ug/m ³
	24 Hours	10.0 ug/m ³ .	4.00ug/m ³	
	Annual			
	24 Hours			
	8 Hours			
	1 Hour			

Note: ug=1x10⁻⁶ gm;

Source: Pollution Control Act, Rules and Notification, Central Pollution Control Board Publication., 2001.

CONCLUSION

In this present research have discussed the causes, sources and classification of air pollution. It dealt with the effects of air pollution on human as well as on plants . It also revealed the status of air pollution on national and International level The air quality standards have been described. Lastly, air quality management aspects have been discussed.

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